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Evaluating the Impact of Students' Attitudes on Waste Management in Federal Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

The global increase in waste generation, driven by accelerated population growth, industrialization and rising consumption, has overwhelmed public waste management systems, necessitating the need for active participation of individuals and institutions in promoting environmental sustainability. Higher education institutions play a crucial role in promoting responsible waste management practices and environmental awareness among students. This study assessed the impact of students' knowledge and behavioural intentions on waste management in Federal Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, with a sample of 386 respondents randomly selected from a population of 11,320 students across the four Federal Colleges using Taro Yamane's sampling formula. Data collected through a structured questionnaire were analyzed using SPSS (version 26) and Smart PLS. The findings revealed a statistically significant relationship between students' knowledge and waste management ($t = 9.260, p < 0.001$), indicating that knowledge has a strong influence on waste management outcomes. Behavioural intention also emerged as a strong predictor of effective waste practices ($t = 8.277, p = 0.000$). The study concludes that awareness of the consequences of improper waste disposal enhances students' willingness to participate in clean-up activities and adopt sustainable waste practices. Although attitude showed limited direct influence, peer interaction, proper orientation, and adequate facilities can strengthen students' commitment to sustainable campus waste management. It is therefore recommended that college administrators integrate waste management principles into the curriculum and create platforms that empower students to serve as sustainability ambassadors promoting environmentally responsible practices within and beyond the campus.

Keywords: Environmental Sustainability, Federal Colleges of Education, Students' Attitudes, Waste Management

Introduction

The sustainable and proper management of solid waste (SWM) has posed serious challenges in terms of economic, social, and environmental factors in many nations of the world, particularly the developing ones (Onungwe, et al., 2023). The common methods of municipal

waste disposal in some developing countries, such as Nigeria, include open burning, incineration, unregulated landfills, and dumping into drain channels, streams, and rivers. These methods create an unhealthy environment and health hazards; they are outdated and inefficient in coping with the high volume of waste. Lissah et al. (2021) identified ineffective enforcement of waste disposal regulations, poor logistics, budgetary restraints, and negative attitudes toward waste management as other contributing factors to inappropriate garbage burning and dumping in many urban cities.

Unregulated waste management has become a global concern, contributing to pollution, environmental degradation, flooding and disease outbreaks in many countries in the world. In Nigeria, for instance, rapid urbanization, industrialization and population growth, since the oil boom era in the 1970s, has drastically increased waste production in cities like Lagos, Abeokuta, Ota, Kano, Calabar, and Port Harcourt. In these cities and other urban centers different kinds of solid waste are carelessly disposed of, posing major risks to the environment and human health (Olalekan, et. al., 2024). Similarly, Volsuuri et al., (2022) observed that many cities in Ghana work with private companies to handle waste but unfortunately, these partnerships are not working well because of issues like lack of transparency, poor accountability, and unfair contract processes leading to indiscriminate disposal of waste.

Waste generation in higher education institutions (HEIs) is also greatly rising due to increased enrolments, consumption patterns and urbanized lifestyles. HEIs, as knowledge centers, are strategically positioned to shape future leaders' perspectives and behaviours regarding environmental sustainability. However, the extent to which students internalize, and practice sustainable waste management remains under-evaluated. Understanding and enhancing students' attitudes towards waste management is crucial in fostering a culture of sustainability within and beyond campus boundaries.

This study seeks to assess students' attitudes toward waste management; to examine how knowledge, attitudes, and behavioural intention of students in Federal Colleges of Education, Southwest, Nigeria affect their solid waste disposal system. This is necessary to properly address several key issues related to waste management within the institutions and also identify areas where education and awareness are lacking.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Wastes are materials for which the initial user or buyer can no longer derive any usefulness in terms of their purpose of production, transformation or consumption and therefore want to dispose of it off. Waste can also be defined as items that are to be discarded because they have no further usefulness and have the potential to cause death, illness or injury to people or destruction to the environment if improperly treated, stored, transported or discarded (Tunji-Olayeni et. al., 2019). **Waste Management** refers to the systematic collection, treatment, and

disposal of waste materials in ways that reduce adverse environmental impacts and enhance resource recovery. Within the context of higher education, effective waste management encompasses practices such as recycling, reuse, and proper disposal (Odeyemi & Adebayo, 2020). Waste management is a global concern and a major component of environmental sustainability issues in both developed and developing countries.

Students' attitude refers to the collective beliefs, perceptions, feelings, and behavioral tendencies that students hold toward environmental practices. This includes students' level of concern for environmental issues, willingness to participate in campus cleaning, engaging in initiatives such as recycling or proper waste segregation, and their sense of responsibility for a sustainable campus environment.

Every school generates waste from routine activities such as classwork, sweeping, serving food, and bush cutting. Waste management activities in schools should involve building the right attitudes in the students toward proper waste management (Debrah, 2021). Educational education and environmental advertising are therefore essential to ensure students have the required knowledge and positive attitudes towards efficient waste management on campus. If school authorities implement environmental education through formal and informal initiatives, the students can impact the environmental knowledge, attitudes, and behaviour to achieve environmental sustainability within the school environment and to influence the adults.

Recent studies have explored various factors influencing students' attitudes with emphasis on how knowledge, perceptions and belief, behavioural intentions and actual actions affect waste management, and affirmed that students' attitudes greatly affect waste management in campuses.

Impact of Students' Attitudes on Waste Management

Students' attitudes towards waste management refer to students' favourable or unfavourable feelings regarding certain characteristics or occurrences in their physical environment that affect their waste management. Students' attitudes toward waste management are largely shaped by their knowledge, perceptions, beliefs, behavioural intentions, and actual practices regarding environmental issues. These attitudes reflect not only their awareness and concern for the environment but also their willingness to participate in campus cleanliness initiatives, engage in green practices such as recycling and proper waste segregation, and demonstrate a sense of personal responsibility toward maintaining a sustainable and healthy campus environment. This was collaborated by Qu et. al. (2023) in a study titled College Students' Attitude towards Waste Separation and Recovery on Campus, carried out to determine and verify the variable relationship, influence path, and regulating factors of college students' waste separation attitude and behaviour. The study discovered that students' knowledge about waste separation significantly influenced their attitudes and behaviors toward waste management.

Students' attitudes play a key role in how well sustainable waste management is practiced in schools and communities. Based on Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour, having a positive attitude toward waste segregation can increase students' willingness to act, but real change depends on supportive conditions. A positive attitude among students toward waste separation is often associated with a greater willingness to engage in such practices; however, this willingness does not always translate into actual behaviour without the presence of supportive conditions. Therefore, fostering a comprehensive understanding of waste management principles is essential for cultivating constructive attitudes and responsible waste-handling behaviours among students.

Impact of Students' Knowledge on Waste Management

Knowledge refers to the extent of information, understanding, and awareness that learners possess about a particular subject such as waste management and environmental sustainability. It includes both theoretical comprehension and practical insights gained by students through environmental education, personal experiences, and social interactions that foster efficient waste management in campuses. Students generally exhibit moderate levels of knowledge about waste management as regards waste classifications, waste management methods, environmental and health implications of improper waste disposal. The level of knowledge depends on environmental education, workshops and seminars on sustainability, clubs, educational posters, workshops, and training. However, this knowledge tends to be superficial, as most students are not thoroughly educated on areas such as hazardous waste handling, composting techniques, and the intricacies of recycling processes. A full understanding of these areas will translate to efficient waste management, which is primarily centered on waste separation and recycling.

Li et al. (2024), in a study investigating the impact of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of university students regarding waste sorting, emphasize that educational interventions, such as environmental education, workshops, and training, are crucial for equipping university students with the knowledge and positive attitudes for effective waste separation on campus. Their study found that students with greater awareness of waste types and disposal methods are more likely to practice proper waste separation. Conversely, Salami et al. (2024) in another study titled "Exploring University Undergraduate Students' Knowledge and Attitudes towards Waste Management, report that university undergraduates generally lack sufficient knowledge about waste management and recommend incorporating relevant topics and practical experiences into the curriculum to improve awareness and attitudes.

Impact of Students' Behavioural Intentions on Waste Management

Behavioural intention is the willingness to participate in an action. Behavioural intention of students to waste management is the willingness of students to engage in waste management

initiatives, it includes their intention to properly dispose of waste even when no one is watching, readiness to educate peers about waste management, adopting sustainable consumption habits (e.g., using reusable items), and willingness to report improper waste disposal by others. This underscores the importance of strengthening students' behavioral intentions through targeted educational interventions and marketing strategies to promote environmentally responsive behaviours among students. Initiatives like environmental advertising and social media platforms with content targeted at efficient waste management messages will help in shaping students' attitudes and perceptions about waste management. Through these means the students are more likely to form a conscious intention to adopt proper waste disposal habits. Educational institutions serve not only as centers of learning but also as platforms for cultivating environmentally responsible behaviour among students and staff. Targeted efforts must be put in place by the school authority to bridge the gap between students' knowledge of proper waste management and their actual behaviour to achieve clean environment within campuses (Sewak et al., 2021).

When adequate knowledge and awareness are communicated to students, they will be enlightened about health hazards from improper waste disposal and hence develop a willingness to participate in appropriate behaviours that safeguard public health through efficient waste management (Olalekan et al., 2024). To achieve a successful waste management program in educational institutions, strategies that promote sustainable waste management behavior, such as incorporating environmental education into the curriculum, developing convenient waste management infrastructure, and implementing social marketing campaigns, are crucial for environmental sustainability on campuses. By adopting these strategies, educational institutions can encourage students to develop sustainable waste management practices that benefit the environment.

Factors Affecting Students' Attitudes

The enormous volume of solid waste has placed immense pressure on the global environment. Institutions of learning, particularly tertiary institutions, play a critical role in shaping sustainable behaviors among future leaders. Unfortunately, despite the evident necessity of responsible waste handling, inadequate environmental education, lack of modern infrastructure, technological and financial limitations, poor policy implementation, as well as students' negative or indifferent attitudes toward waste management practices are some of the factors hindering the effective student involvement in waste management.

Inadequate Environmental Education - Environmental education plays a vital role in efficient waste management, particularly in developing countries for raising awareness, changing attitudes, and promoting sustainable practices and evolving positive attitudes towards waste separation on campus. However, students often lack foundational knowledge about the

environmental impact of waste and the importance of proper waste management (Adeolu et al., 2021). Even where they are taught, it is often theoretical and devoid of practical engagement.

Poor Waste Management Infrastructure - The absence of adequate bins, recycling centers, and waste segregation mechanisms in schools discourages students from participating actively in efficient waste management. In many campuses, students are confronted with overfilled bins and poor collection systems, coupled with indiscipline among the maintenance staff who often leave the overfilled bins unattended (Usman et al., 2023). The installation of colour-coded waste bins will encourage students to separate their waste while disposing of them.

Policy and Institutional Gaps - Many educational institutions fail to enforce environmental policies and mechanisms that guide students' participation in waste management, even when they exist. Enforcement is often weak or inconsistently applied due to human factors. Considering the deleterious health effects of improper waste management, strict enforcement of policy is necessary on campuses to encourage proper waste management by all occupants, whether students or staff.

Lack of Incentives and Student Engagement - Students are often not actively involved in the planning or execution of the waste management programme due to the non-availability of incentives as motivators. The absence of reward systems or gamified approaches also reduces students' enthusiasm for participation in efficient waste management (Park et al., 2020). Incentives in the form of deposit and refund systems will motivate responsible waste behaviour among students.

Technological Limitations - In the digital age, students are highly responsive to media and mobile technologies. However, there is often a lack of innovative tools such as waste management apps, digital reminders, or interactive waste tracking platforms in school settings to enhance efficient waste monitoring and management (Kumi-Larbi et al., 2024).

Theoretical Review

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) - The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1991), assumes that a person who has a positive attitude towards a particular behaviour has a greater intention to involve in this behaviour and that an individual's behaviour is determined by three factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Ramkissoon, 2021). Positive attitudes, subjective norms and perceived control are major determinants of students' waste separation behaviour; it is therefore important to reinforce attitudinal orientation of students in shaping environmental sustainability on campuses.

Social Marketing Theory - Social marketing theory introduced by Kotler & Zaltman (1971) support the use of marketing principles such as green campaigns through social media platforms, and incentives to influence behaviours that benefit individuals and communities for the greater social good. In higher education institutions, this involves making waste separation and recycling more visible, rewarding, and accessible to students. Thus, social marketing

complements attitudinal change by converting awareness into structured behavioral adoption. Student participation in waste management increases significantly when campaigns are structured around relatable incentives, convenient waste disposal facilities, and peer-driven promotional strategies (Ramayah, et al., 2022).

Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) - PMT, developed by Rogers (1975), is concerned with how individuals assess threats and take action to protect themselves against the dangers of inefficient waste management. Since the waste disposal process poses environmental and health risks and also contributes to global climate change, it is possible that an individual's threat appraisal and coping appraisal, as indicated in PMT, may influence their engagement in efficient waste management practices (Janmaimool, 2017).

The above theories provide a strong framework for examining how students in higher educational institutions manage their waste. TPB positions attitude as a crucial predictor of behavioural intention within social and institutional contexts, PMT offers insight into threat perception and coping effectiveness, and Social Marketing Theory connects intention and action through carefully planned interventions. The combination of these viewpoints emphasizes that although awareness and knowledge are fundamental, students need both motivating factors and supportive surroundings to engage in sustainable waste management methods.

Empirical Review

Several studies have provided practical insights into how students' attitudes, knowledge, and behavioral intentions influence their waste management behaviors in Federal Colleges of Education in Southwest Nigeria. By examining previous research on the participation of students in higher education institutions in waste separation, recycling, and environmentally sustainable behaviors, this section highlights the practical implications of the theoretical frameworks of the Theory of Planned Behavior and Social Marketing Theory in Waste Management.

An empirical study on college students' attitudes toward waste separation and recovery revealed that female students demonstrated more positive attitudes and responsiveness to waste-related issues than their male counterparts. Moreover, the study found a positive correlation between students' knowledge of waste management and their propensity to engage in environmentally responsible behaviours and thus concludes that understanding students' attitudes and their environment can help schools and policymakers create better waste management systems on campus (Qu, et al., 2023).

A study by Salami et al., (2024) titled exploring university undergraduate students' knowledge and attitudes towards waste management revealed that although university students have moderate knowledge of waste management, their attitudes and disposal behaviours are inconsistent and inadequate. The study recommends incorporating environmental education

and practical activities into the curriculum to enhance students’ awareness and promote responsible waste management practices.

Jerath, (2021) in a study title “Awareness and Attitude of Students towards Municipal Solid Waste Management to Achieve Sustainable Development Goals - A Case Study” which focused on assessing students’ perception, understanding, and behaviour towards environment and sustainable development, with a focus on municipal solid waste management using questionnaire-based approach reveals that although students have knowledge and awareness about waste management, they lack motivation for waste segregation and composting. This highlights the urgent need to enhance students’ sensitization through various means of green campaign strategies, such as environmental advertising, social media platforms, and incentives, to channel their potential towards sustainable waste management (Oreagba & Azeez, 2025).

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the impact of students’ attitudes, knowledge, and behavioral intentions on waste management in Federal Colleges of Education in South-West Nigeria. The population consisted of 11,320 students drawn from four Federal Colleges selected to ensure regional representation. A sample size of 386 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula, which was selected using a simple random sampling technique across the institutions. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire developed from a review of the literature, covering students’ knowledge, attitudes, behavioral intentions, and waste management practices. Items were rated on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1).

The instrument’s content validity was confirmed through expert review, and its reliability was established via a pilot test with 40 students, yielding Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients between 0.81 and 0.86, which confirmed internal consistency. The data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 26 for descriptive statistics and SmartPLS for inferential analysis through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to test the hypothesized relationships at a 0.05 significance level.

Result

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Students’ Attitude

Knowledge and awareness	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is enough awareness of environmental cleanliness on my campus.	2.61	.942
Recycling education is part of the orientation programmes in my college.	2.60	.944
Attractive campaign messages on signposts motivate my positive response to a clean environment.	2.57	.885
I possess a solid understanding of solid waste management.	2.62	.908

I know where to take my recyclable items for reprocessing.	2.74	.868
Behavioural Intention		
I take the initiative to promote cleanliness around me.	2.69	.893
I use reusable bags and containers to carry my items of food and drinks.	2.67	.908
I separate waste based on the colour-coded bins provided.	2.68	.916
I always take reusable bags and containers with me for shopping.	2.66	.929
I volunteer to clean up trash in the school environment.	2.67	.928

Table 1 presents an analysis of students' attitudes. The analysis, presented in the form of means and standard deviations, focuses on knowledge and awareness, as well as behavioural intentions. The table shows that the respondents had a high response to the items measuring knowledge and awareness, but a low response to the items that said attractive campaign messages on signposts as motivation for a clean environment. The table also reveals that the respondents had a high response to the items measuring the behavioural intention but gave a low response to the items that said they volunteer to clean up trash in the school environment and use reusable bags and containers to carry their items of food and drink.

Regression Analysis on knowledge-based and waste management

	B	Std. Error	t	R	F	Sig.
Knowledge Based	0.328	0.035	9.260	0.440	85.740	0.000

Dependent Variable: Waste Management

Note: B - unstandardized coefficients

The unstandardized coefficient (B = 0.328) indicates that a one-unit increase in knowledge-based strategies results in a 0.328-unit increase in effective waste management. The correlation coefficient is moderate (R = 0.440), which shows a moderate correlation between knowledge-based strategies and waste management. The t-value is high, and the significance level is below 0.05, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant (t = 9.260, p < 0.001). Knowledge-based strategies have a significant predictive and influential impact on waste management outcomes. This suggests that improving individuals' or learners' knowledge levels leads to more responsible and effective waste management behaviours.

Regression Analysis on behavioural intention and waste management

	B	Std. Error	t	R	F	Sig.
Behavioural Intention	0.305	0.037	8.277	0.401	68.517	0.000

Dependent Variable: Waste Management

Note: B - unstandardized coefficients, t (t-value), R - correlation coefficients, F - F-statistic
The unstandardized coefficient (B = 0.305) indicates that a one-unit increase in behavioural intention leads to a 0.305-unit increase in effective waste management. The correlation coefficient is moderate (R = 0.401), which shows a moderate correlation between behavioural intention and waste management. The t-value is high, and the significance level is below 0.05, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant (t = 8.277, p < 0.001). Behavioural intention is a **strong predictor** of waste management, suggesting that when individuals have a strong intention to act, it translates into improved environmental practices.

Discussion of Findings

Although descriptive analysis revealed high behavioural intentions (e.g., students engaging in waste separation and using reusable containers), there is a low response to the item that said they volunteer to clean up trash in the school environment and use reusable bags. This suggests that students' attitudes may not translate into actual behaviour change towards proper waste management. There are other factors, such as provision of infrastructure, environmental education and the university policy, that affect waste behaviour apart from individual attitude. This could imply that other factors exert a stronger influence on waste management practices among students; such factors should be integrated by campus management to support a more coordinated and effective approach to waste management on campuses. The result is consistent with previous scholars who observed a gap between attitude and practice (Abdulfatah, 2023; Jakimiuk et al., 2023).

Conclusion

This study highlights the important role of students' attitudes in influencing waste management practices in higher education institutions. Drawing on insights from the Theory of Planned Behavior, Protection Motivation Theory, and Social Marketing Theory, it is evident that positive attitudes, perceived control, and environmental awareness significantly influence students' motivation to manage waste sustainably. However, findings show that positive attitudes alone do not always lead to actual behaviour change; it is necessary to combine students' attitudes with supportive infrastructure, environmental education, and strong institutional policies to build a culture of environmental responsibility aligned with global sustainability goals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance waste management in the Federal Colleges of Education in the Southwest, Nigeria.

- i. Institutions can integrate waste management principles and environmental sustainability training into various academic disciplines.
- ii. Fostering positive attitudes towards waste management is crucial for overall engagement and long-term sustainability efforts.
- iii. Management should involve students in hands on practical activities on waste management tasks like sorting waste, recycling projects, and campus clean-up events.
- iv. Empower and train students as sustainability ambassadors or peer educators to take active participation in proper waste separation and lead discussions among their peers.

References

- Abdulfatah, A. K. (2023). *Exploring municipal solid waste management in Nigeria: Challenges, opportunities, and roadmap for sustainable development* (PhD thesis, School of Business and Law, The University of Salford).
- Adeolu, A. T., Enesi, D. O., & Ojedokun, A. O. (2021). Environmental education and recycling habits among Nigerian university students. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 34(2), 115–130.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211.
- Debrah, J. K., Vidal, D. G., & Dinis, M. A. P. (2021). Raising awareness on solid waste management through formal education for sustainability: A developing countries evidence reviews. *Recycling*, 6(6).
- Dixon, J., & Parker, J. (2022). Don't be a waster! Student perceptions of recycling strategies at an English university's halls of residence. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 23(3), 461–477.
- Ibrahim, S., & Amin, A. (2023). Developing a sustainable approach to waste management in Nigeria: Lessons from Kwara State. *Lafia Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 8(2), 183–202.
- Jakimiuk, A., Matsui, Y., Podlasek, A., Koda, E., Goli, V. S. N. S., & Voberkova, S. (2023). Closing the loop: A case study on pathways for promoting sustainable waste management on university campuses. *Science of The Total Environment*, 892, 164349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164349>
- Janmaimool, P. (2017). Application of protection motivation theory to investigate sustainable waste management behaviors. *Sustainability*, 9(1079).

- Jerath, N. (2021). Awareness and attitude of students towards municipal solid waste management to achieve sustainable development goals – A case study. *International Journal of Plant and Environment*, 7(1), 78–85.
- Kumi-Larbi, J. A., Owusu, K., Boakye, P. Y., & Mensah, N. Y. (2024). Technology and sustainable waste practices in West African universities. *Sustainability Journal*, 16(4), 1202.
- Li, Y., Wang, Z., & Zhang, X. (2024). Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of university students regarding waste sorting in Beijing, China. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, Article 1328583. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1328583>
- Lissah, S. Y., Ayanore, M. A., Krugu, J. K., Aberese-Ako, M., & Ruiter, R. A. (2021). Managing urban solid waste in Ghana: Perspectives and experiences of municipal waste company managers and supervisors in an urban municipality. *PLOS ONE*, 16(3), e0248392.
- Olalekan, O. S., Akanbi-Gada, A. M., Iyanda, Y. A., & Ishola, B. A. (2024). Exploring university undergraduate students' knowledge and attitudes towards waste management. *KWASU International Journal of Education*, 7(1), 120–129. <https://www.kije.com.n>
- Odeyemi, A. M., & Adebayo, K. O. (2020). Institutional approaches to solid waste management in Nigeria. *Environmental Management Review*, 12(4), 56–69.
- Onungwe, I., Hunt, D. V. L., & Jefferson, I. (2023). Transition and implementation of circular economy in municipal solid waste management system in Nigeria: A systematic review of the literature. *Sustainability*, 15(16), 12602.
- Park, J., Kim, H., & Lee, S. (2020). Gamification in sustainability education: A case study on recycling. *Education for Sustainable Development Review*, 3(1), 29–42.
- Qu, D., Shevchenko, T., Shams Esfandabadi, Z., & Ranjbari, M. (2023). College students' attitude towards waste separation and recovery on campus. *Sustainability*, 15(1620). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021620>
- Ramayah, T., Lee, J. W. C., & Lim, S. (2022). Applying social marketing strategies to encourage recycling behavior among university students. *Sustainability*, 14(12), 7008. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127008>
- Ramkissoon, H. (2023). Integrating pro-environmental behaviour into urban waste management: A TPB-based approach. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 86, 102008.
- Rogers, R. W. (1975). A protection motivation theory of fear appeals and attitude change. *Journal of Psychology*, 91, 93–114.
- Sewak, A., Kim, J., Rundle-Thiele, S., & Deshpande, S. (2021). Influencing household-level waste sorting and composting behaviour: What works? A systematic review (1995–2020). *Research*, 39(7), 892–909.

- Tunji-Olayeni, P., Osabuohien, E., Yabkwa, S., & Ademola, A. (2019). Youth employment creation as an inclusive solution for sustainable development: Lessons from the ‘Double You’ digital skills initiative in Nigeria. *Earth and Environmental Science, World Bank*.
- Usman, A. M., Ibrahim, S., & Lawal, A. (2023). Assessing waste infrastructure and student behavior in northern Nigerian polytechnics. *Waste and Resource Management Journal, 39*(3), 200–214.
- Volsuuri, E., Owusu-Sekyere, E., & Imoro, A. Z. (2022). Rethinking solid waste governance in Ghana. *Heliyon, 8*(12), e12235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e12235>